

ROLE OF HOMOEOPATHIC TREATMENT IN A CASE OF FIBROADENOMA: A CASE REPORT

¹Dr. Atul Kumar Singh, ²Dr. Aditya Sharma, ³Dr. Abdul Wahid, ⁴Dr. Mukesh Sengar, ⁵Dr. Yogendra Meena, ^{6*}Dr. Nitesh Rathore

¹MD, PhD, HOD, MNHMC and RI, Bikaner.

²MD, Department of Physiology, MNHMC and RI, Bikaner.

³MD, Department of Materia Medica, MNHMC and RI, Bikaner.

⁴BHMS, Department of Materia Medica, MNHMC and RI Bikaner.

⁵MD, Department of Physiology, MNHMC & RI, Bikaner).

⁶(BHMS, INTERN, MNHMC and RI, Bikaner).

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Nitesh Rathore

(BHMS, INTERN, MNHMC and
RI, Bikaner).

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ABSTRACT

Fibroadenoma is a common complaint in the reproductive age of female. Fibroadenoma is a painless, unilateral, benign breast tumour. Homoeopathic medicine plays important role in the treatment of fibroadenoma. 10% of the world's female population suffers from fibroadenoma once in their lifetime. Many homoeopathic medicines show very good result in fibroadenoma of the breast. **Case Summary:** This is a case of 22-year-old female suffering from fibroadenoma. The presenting complaints included pain in right breast with lump and fibroadenosis changes in both breast, which was treated with homocopathic medicine. The case was thoroughly analysed and treated with homoeopathic medicine Calcarea flourica 6X and Lapis albus. Regular follow-ups were taken and the patient improved significantly both symptomatically as

well as clinically, assessed by USG.

INTRODUCTION^[1]

Fibroadenoma is a painless, unilateral, benign (non-cancerous) growth of breast, it is a solid, not fluid-filled, lump. It occurs most usually in females between the age of fourteen to thirty-

five years however it can at any age. Fibroadenomas shrink after biological time/ menopause, and thus, uncommon in post-menopausal females or climacteric age. Fibroadenomas are often referred to as a breast mouse due to their high mobility. Fibroadenomas are a marble-like mass comprising both epithelial and stromal tissues located under the breast skin. These breast masses are firm, rubbery with regular borders are often variable in size. It is known that 10% of the world's female population suffers from fibroadenoma once in their whole life.

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 22 year old girl complaint about a pain in right breast with lump she recently discovered on self-examination.

HOPC

Patient was apparently well 10 days back when she noticed a lump in right breast and stitching pain in breast. Gradually increased to present size. Persistent pains in breast, increase before and during menses with fullness sensation in breast and radiate to scapulae region. Pain increase by motion.

PAST HISTORY: PCOD treated by allopathic medicine.

CLINICAL FINDINGS

The patient's physical generals revealed a good appetite and a daily water intake of 2-3 litres. She had specific desire of cold drinks, while she was averse to meat. Her bowel movements were irregular and unsatisfactory, urine was clear. menses are scanty, black in colour, flow only for two days. Abdominal pain at beginning of menses.

DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT

Bilateral breast examination

Lump palpable in upper outer quadrant in right breast and fibroadenosis changes in both breast.

Investigation: Usg of B/L breast with axilla

Fig. No. 1: (The usg report showed 22x10mm oval shaped hypochoic lesion in right breast. (BIRADS-3).

Fig. no. 2: 1(the usg report showed 21x10mm oval shaped hypochoic lesion in right breast (birads-3).

Fibroadenosis changes in both breast

Fig. No. 2.2.

APSARA LAB & IMAGING CENTER
Opp. P.B.M. Hospital, Bikaner (Raj.) M: 9024474466, 7611000101

Patient: [REDACTED] Age: 22 Yrs/F Date: 17 December 2025
Ref by - DR. MEDICAL OFFICER

USG BOTH BREAST

- Multiple, tiny, nodular lesions of very small in sizes with prominent fibrostromal matrix noted in B/L breast.
- A well defined, oval, hypochoic, lobulated lesion, having homogenous internal echo pattern of low reflectivity, of size about 20x14 mm noted at 10 O'clock position in right breast. The lesion is surrounded by thin capsule & causing posterior acoustic enhancement.
- No evidence of any architectural distortion.
- No evidence of any calcification is seen.
- The pectoralis muscles show a homogeneous echopattern.
- Subareolar & retromammary regions is unremarkable.
- Lactiferous duct are not dilated.
- No evidence of lymphadenopathy.

IMPRESSION:

- MILD CHANGES OF FIBROADENOSIS B/L BREAST.
- FIBROADENOMA RIGHT BREAST.

Dr. V.K. CHAUDHARY (MD pathologist, Ex. Professor & Head, Reg. No.: 2017, Dt. 29-4-88) Dr. Surendra Poonia (MBBS, MD, DM (Cardiology), RMC No.: 025497) Dr. P.M. Sareen (M.D.) (Retd. Prof. & Head Pathologist) Dr. PUSHP SHARMA (M.D., (RADIO DIAGNOSIS), RMC No. 22730/9916)

TECHNICIAN

This is only Professional Opinion and not the Diagnosis. Kindly Correlate clinically. This report is not valid of MLC Purpose. Subject to Bikaner Jurisdiction.

Fig. No. 3.1: (The Usg report showed 20x14 mm oval shaped hypochoic lesion in right breast).

Fibroadenosis changes in both breast

Fig. no. 3.2.

DEPARTMENT OF RADIODIAGNOSIS
 Prince Bijay Singh Ji Memorial (P.B.M.) Hospital & AG Of Hospitals, Bikaner (Raj.)

SONOGRAPHY REPORT

Name : Age & Sex : (F)
 Reg. No: 16 Date : 25/3/20

Liver : USG - VS/L Breast

Gall Bladder : (RT) few lymph nodes noted in largest
 78x8 mm. E maintained fatty hilum

CBD :

Pancreas : Approx 10x15mm, lower hypoechoic
 well defined lobulated at 10:00 position

Spleen :
 a (R) breast

Kidneys: Right
 Left
 1/0 BIRADS-2 / fibroadenoma

UB :

Prostate :
 @ breast - increased fibroglandular
 tissue noted

Uterus & Adnexa :
 1/0 fibroadenoma

Specific: Free fluid : Bowel loops:

Lymphnodes :

Others :

Impression :

Advice :

Signature of Radiologist

Fig. No. 4: (The Usg report showed 10x15mm oval shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast.) BIRADS-2. and fibroadenosis changes in breast.

TOTALITY OF SYMPTOMS

- 1) TUMOR IN BREAST.
- 2) PERSISTENT PAIN IN BREAST
- 3) PAIN INCREASE BEFORE AND DURING MENSES.
- 4) STITCHING PAIN IN BREAST.
- 5) FULLNESS FEELING IN BREAST.
- 6) PAIN BETWEEN SCAPULA.
- 7) ABDOMEN PAIN AT BEGINNING OF MENSES.

8) PAIN AGGRAVATED BY MOTION

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

The above symptoms were converted into rubrics, and the case was repertorised using kent repertory in radar opus.2.1.11-license:119669.

- 1) Chest-pain-mammae
- 2) Chest-pain-mammae-menses-before
- 3) Chest-pain-mammae-menses-during
- 4) Chest-pain-stitching-mammae
- 5) Chest-Tumors-mammae
- 6) Chest-fullness-mammae
- 7) Back-pain-dorsal region-scapulae
- 8) Generals-motion-agg.

PRESCRIPTION

Based on totality of symptoms, homoeopathic medicine conium maculatum30, BD was prescribed for 10 days, There was slight relief in pain, so the medicine was repeated and potency was increased to Conium maculatum 200, OD for 20 days in second prescription(fig.1). After this, Usg was done, (fig.2) which showed no reduction in size of lump, no much relief in pain, following this, phytolacca decandra Q, BD was prescribed for 3 months. Another usg was performed, (fig.3) which showed no reduction in size of lump. Subsequently, due to persistent pain in mammary region and glandular hardening, prescribed Lapis albus 30, BD and Calcarea fluorica 6X(6-6)BD, for 3 months and usg was done,(fig.4)report showed reduction in size of lump and relief in pain. Therefore, the medicine was repeated and potency was increased to lapis albus 200, OD with calcarea fluorica 6X(6-6)BD for 3 month.

FOLLOW-UPS AND OUTCOME

DATE OF VISIT	SYMPTOMS	USG FINDINGS	PRESCRIPTION
5/8/25	1) Pain in breast with lump. 2) Pain increase by motion	Fig.1) The Usg report showed 22x10mm oval shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast(BIRADS-3), Fibroadenosis changes in both breast	Conium maculatum 30 BD For 10 Days.
15/8/25	1) Slight relief in pain with lump	Fig.1) The Usg report showed 22x10mm oval	Conium maculatum 200 OD.

	2) Pain increase by motion.	shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast (BIRADS-3), Fibroadenosis changes in both breast.	For 20 days.
6/9/25	1) Slight relief in pain and not much decreased in size of lump. 2) Pain increase by motion.	Fig.2) The Usg report showed 21x10mm oval shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast (BIRADS-3), Fibroadenosis changes in both breast.	Phytolacca decandra Q BD For 3 month
18/12/25	1) Temporary relief in pain 2) Not change in size of lump	Fig.3) The Usg report showed 20x14 mm oval shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast, Fibroadenosis changes in both breast.	Lapis albus 30 BD, Calcarea fluorica 6X.(6 -6) BD. For 3 month
26/3/26	1) Decrease in size of lump. 2) Relief in pain	Fig.4) The Usg report showed 10x15mm oval shaped hypoechoic lesion in right breast.	Lapis albus 200 OD And Calcarea fluorica 6X.(6-6)BD. For 3 month

CONCLUSION

After administering Conium maculatum and Phytolacca decandra, no significant relief was observed. Subsequently, Lapis albus and Calcarea fluorica, were prescribed, which resulted in a reduction in both the size of the tumor and the associated pain. Therefore, continued for three months. After this period, an ultrasound (USG) will be advised to assess the size of the tumor.

REFERENCE

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